

Medical Education Coordinator Jessica Alvarez (she/her)

“Working with colleagues across departments and helping them improve their training programs allows me to see the true impact of my work.”

Bio

Jessica has worked as a Medical Education Coordinator for the past four years. Her main tasks include devising and implementing educational programs for the clinical and research workforce. Using her thorough knowledge of the institutional vision, program objectives, and national and international compliance requirements, she liaises with various units and directors to identify and fill in training gaps. Previous nursing experiences have given her valuable insights about patient care and its challenges, and the required training for improving it in different clinical settings. She is gaining research skills through partnerships with faculty researchers and seeks out trainings in adult education and project management to support her role.

Much of Jessica's role revolves around communication with different stakeholders. Daily, she can be found in online meetings with team members or department heads or communicating with them over email.

Education: Bachelor of Science in Nursing
Years of experience: 4
Work location: University, clinic sites, remote work on laptop; travel to training sites

Goals

- Improve the quality of medical education programs through instructional design skills
- Support the medical education program's efforts to publish more consistently
- Create a strategic plan to identify gaps and set long term goals for programs, ensure alignment with competencies, and help maintain accreditation
- Communicate impact to receive more funding support to continue the work
- Design a coherent and inclusive learning experience
- Prepare the clinical and research workforce to prepare for and build resilience for future emergencies, (e.g., pandemic)

Software attitude & use

- Not a tech-savvy person, uses library classes to learn new software
- General: Microsoft Office Suite and Google Workspace
- Collaboration: Slack, Zoom and other video conference software
- Specialized resources include presentation tools (e.g., Camtasia, Captivate, PowerPoint), REDCap, bibliographic resources (e.g., PubMed, Google Scholar)

Pain Points

- Lack of synergy between departments with different focuses and goals
- Lack of time to learn and use new technologies
- Coordinating multiple schedules
- Tracking training impact
- Overwhelming number of emails

Motivators

- Provide educational programming that encourages career development and improves patient care
- Create educational opportunities and programs in research settings that are more accessible to a diverse research workforce
- Develop a sustainable and impactful program model that can be adapted and reproduced in the future

Outputs

- Conference posters
- Curriculum and lecture notes

Wants/Needs

- Gain confidence in her role as an educational leader
- Build collaborations between well-established units and break down research silos
- A team with instructional designers and technologists to improve delivered programs
- Tools and resources to manage the high volume of email and Slack communication she receives

Professional Development

Jessica attends scholarly conferences like AMEE and AAMC to present, network with other educators, and participate in training workshops

Jessica obtained Certified Healthcare Simulation Educator (CHSE®) certification

Jessica enrolled in a training at her institution to learn more about the research process, constituents, gaps, and pain points in clinical research